

Quantum Mechanics, Statistical Indistinguishability and Brownian Motion

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Brownian motion is formulated in the form d/dt (partial) spatial density = $D d/dx d/dx$ density. This motion is generalized in the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck case (1) to: d/dt (partial) density(v) = bd/dv {v density(v) + $kT d/dv$ density(v)/m} which yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann equilibrium distribution $C \exp(-.5mv^2/T)$. It is also generalized in the Smoluchowski case (1) to:

d/dt (partial) density = d/dx (density dV/dx + kTd/dx density)/mb which yields the equilibrium result (d/dt partial density =0) of $C \exp(-V(x)/T)$ where $V(x)$ is the potential.

In a previous note (2), we argued that for quantum mechanical equilibrium one may try to apply Brownian motion to the relative conditional probability i.e. the wavefunction $W(x,t)$. In such a case, the equilibrium requirement is no longer d/dt partial density=0. In this note, we try to consider the nonrelativistic Brownian motion equation for $W(x,t)$ in terms of statistical indistinguishability. We argue that statistical indistinguishability occurs at two levels. First, there is an inherent indistinguishability for a quantum particle with constant p to be at any x , yet there is a probability flow proportional to p . This suggests $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution, but $\exp(ipx)$ is also a solution of a Brownian motion equation with d/dt partial $W(x,t) = -iE$. For the case of a potential $V(x)$, a second stochastic process occurs. By taking the time independent Schrodinger equation and replacing $W(x,t)$ and $V(x)$ by Fourier series we find:

$$E a_p = a_p p^2/2m + \sum_k V_k a_{(p-k)} \quad ((1))$$

This suggests that $V(x)$ is an average describing stochastic hits which give rise to a momentum distribution at each x . Each constant momentum is associated with $\exp(ipx)$ and a weight $a(p)$ and undergoes double stochastic motion (due to $p^2/2m$ Brownian motion and $V(x)$). Statistical indistinguishability suggests that for any p , the two Brownian motions are distinguishable only by $a(p)$ which we argue is the statement of ((1)).

We also show that statistical indistinguishability occurs in classical statistical mechanics. First, the full MB distribution $C \exp(-.5/m p^2/T - V/T) = C \exp(-E/T)$ utilizes statistical indistinguishability at different x points. Secondly, the term {v density + $kT d/dv$ density/m} in the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck case follows from statistical indistinguishability, as will be shown.

Classical Statistical Mechanics and Brownian Motion

The Ornstein-Uhlenbeck and Smoluchowski differential equations are related to Einstein's Brownian motion equation:

$$d/dt$$
 (partial) spatial density = $D d/dx d/dx$ density ((2))

For the equilibrium case, d/dt (partial) density is set to 0 The Ornstein-Uhlenbeck equation yields:

$$\{v \text{ density} + kT d/dv \text{ density}/m\} = \text{constant} \quad ((3))$$

Setting the constant equal to zero leads to an MB solution of $C \exp(-pp/2mT)$. In addition, one sees the diffusion “velocity” $d/dv \ln(\text{density})$ appear. Here a d/dv derivative appears because one considers changes in velocity v and density is $\text{density}(v)$.

For the equilibrium case, the Somochulski differential equation yields:

$$(\text{density} dV/dx + kTd/dx \text{ density}) = \text{constant} \quad ((4))$$

Setting the constant to zero, yields the solution $C2 \exp(-V(x)/T)$.

A full MB solution is: $C \exp(-pp/2mT -V(x)/T)$ ((5))

The above results follow from Brownian motion type equations, each with a diffusion velocity namely $d/dv \ln(\text{density}(v))$ and $d/dx \ln(\text{density}(x))$.

Statistical Indistinguishability in Classical Statistical Mechanics

The above results also follow from statistical indistinguishability with no recourse to Brownian motion being necessary. For the Uhlenbeck-Ornstein equilibrium case, consider a balance of time reversed two body elastic scattering. Statistical indistinguishability occurs because given $p1$ and $p2$, all $p3$ and $p4$ scattering outcomes are possible provided momentum and kinetic energy are conserved. Thus:

$$f(p1)f(p2) = f(p3)f(p4) \text{ and } e1+e2=e3+e4 \text{ where } ei = pipi/2m \quad ((6))$$

Taking \ln of ((6)) and equating to the energy conservation equation yields $\exp(-pp/2mT)$.

((6)), however, is identical to the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck case as shown in (3) i.e. considering $p1=p3+dp$ and using $e1+e2=e3+e4$.

Thus, there is a direct link between statistical indistinguishability and Brownian type motion.

A second situation in which statistical indistinguishability arises is in classical statistical mechanics for the case of an MB gas with a potential $V(x)$. Temperature equilibrium is established through two body scattering which occurs at a point x . Thus, the potential at x does nothing to change this scattering and $\text{density}(v)$ is still $\exp(-pp/2mT)$. The potential changes the kinetic energy of a particle with energy $pp/2mT$ as it moves from one point to another. Thus, $p1p1/2m + V(x1) = p2p2/2m + V(x2)$ ((7)). There is indistinguishability in ((7)) and the full solution with a potential is $\exp(-pp/2mT -V/T)$. A $v1$ at $x1$ has the same probability as a $v2$ at $x2$. For classical statistical mechanics, one has many particles, but may consider a classical

particle as it changes from stochastically. If it does not participate in a two body collision for a short time, then it moves strictly under the influence of the potential $V(x)$ i.e. under Newton's second law.

In quantum mechanics, this is not the case. There is a momentum distribution at each x , but the equilibrium itself is created by stochastic hits with the potential and so the particle does not move under Newton's second law. Newton's law applies to the average rms velocity which follows from the average kinetic energy (which involves interfering terms).

Quantum Mechanics, Brownian Motion and Statistical Indistinguishability

In (2), we argue that one may apply a nonrelativistic Brownian motion equation to the relative conditional probability. In doing so, we already consider the idea of statistical indistinguishability with Brownian motion. Consider a particle with constant momentum p . Statistically, it has the same probability to be at any x , so $P(x)=\text{constant}$. Yet, the particle is moving, so one would expect relative probability to change in x proportional to p . A combination which allows for both of these conditions is $P(p/x) \text{ relative} = \exp(ipx)$ and $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$. Thus, the modulus is constant, but there is still a kind of Brownian motion occurring because $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution of:

$$d/dt W(x,t) = D d/dx d/dx W(x,t) \quad ((8))$$

(Note: imaginary i 's appear in this new solution.) Thus, as argued in (2), we think a Brownian motion equation in quantum mechanics should be based on the wavefunction $W(x,t)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is an interesting solution because there is a humping or resolution pattern based on p . This manifests itself experimentally in two slit experiments etc

The question then becomes how to incorporate a potential $V(x)$. If one considers $V(x)$ to be the average of a stochastic potential, then there exists Brownian motion yielding $\exp(ipx)$ and a second process of stochastic potential hits allowing for transitions from $\exp(i p_i x)$ to $\exp(i p_j x)$. How does one incorporate stochastic motion from a potential? We argue that statistical indistinguishability yields a clue. At each x , one has a momentum distribution:

$$a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ describes Brownian motion due to ((8)), yet there is a second stochastic process due to $V(x)$ which changes $\exp(i p_j x)$ into $\exp(i p_i x)$. We argue statistical indistinguishability should lead to a Brownian motion equation for each $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which only depends on $a(p)$ times a Constant. Examining the time-independent Schrodinger equation shows such a result if one writes $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as Fourier series i.e.

$$E a(p) = a(p) p^2/2m + \text{Sum over } k V(k) a(p-k) \quad ((10))$$

One may write $E a(p) = i d/dt a(p) \exp(-iEt)$. Thus, ((10)) contains the $p^2/2m$ Brownian motion term and a stochastic term in which stochastic components of the potential convert $\exp(i p_j x)$ into $\exp(ipx)$. The combination is a two Brownian motion equation ((10)).

The full two Brownian motion equation is:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t) + V(x) W(x,t) \quad ((11))$$

In the time independent case, one sees that the statistical indistinguishability constant E is energy. Thus, one could have obtained ((11)) without the idea of statistical indistinguishability and used only $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and conservation of average energy. We thus, argue that conservation of average energy follows from statistical indistinguishability.

Brownian Motion at a Single Particle Momentum Level

The “Brownian motion” or “statistical indistinguishability case” of $\exp(ipx)$ is important because it leads to periodic hump-like results. Even in the case of a potential $V(x)$, the $\exp(ipx)$ structure is not destroyed so the final $W(x) = \sum a(p) \exp(ipx)$ also may exhibit humps which are characteristic of quantum mechanics.

Relativistic Considerations

The above arguments apply to the nonrelativistic case. For the Klein-Gordon equation: $EE = pp + m^2$, pp again has the appearance of Brownian motion i.e. $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$, but the potential, whether it is added to E or m^2 , behaves in a very different manner from the nonrelativistic case. There is a VW term which suggests double stochastic hits from the potential if the above holds.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may consider the free quantum particle relative conditional probability $\exp(ipx)$ as due both to statistical indistinguishability in x i.e. $P(x) = \text{constant} = W^*W$ and as a solution of a Brownian motion type equation $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } W = D \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$. For the case of a stochastic potential $V(x)$, one retains Brownian motion at a p level, but considers a momentum distribution due to V . The role of the potential is completely different from that of the MB gas in which two body collisions represent stochastic hits and $V(x)$ simply affects the momentum according to Newton’s second law. We suggest that for the quantum case, one may use statistical indistinguishability i.e. assume each $\exp(ipx)$ has as weight $a(p)$ which is the only distinguishing factor in the double Brownian motion. Thus:

$$E a(p) \text{ from } \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } W(x,t) = a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} + \sum_k V(k) a(p-k) \quad ((12))$$

This, in turn, is: $i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + VW$. For the time-independent Schrodinger equation case, ((12)) is conservation of average energy, but in this note we argue that such conservation follows from statistical indistinguishability.

References

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